

PUBLIC/PRIVATE SECTOR INVOLVEMENT AND SUSTAINABILITY OF CONTRIBUTORY PENSION SCHEME IN NIGERIA

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Abstract: *The study evaluated the public/private sector involvement and sustainability of contributory pension scheme in Nigeria. The specific objectives are to: examine the relationship between contributory pension scheme and maintenance costs of the employees and assess the relationship between defined benefit scheme and operational safety of the employees. The study used a descriptive survey design. It also adopted simple random sampling technique in selecting the sample unit and the population of the study was two hundred and seventy-one (271) comprising of retirees and potential retirees from Enugu metropolis. The whole population was used due to small number. A total of 259 respondents returned the questionnaire accurately filled. Data were presented and analyzed using mean score and standard deviation using Sprint Likert Scale. The hypotheses were analyzed using t - test. The findings indicated that contributory pension scheme had significant positive relationship with the maintenance costs of the employees $t(95, n= 259)$, 9.098, $p. > .05$. Defined benefit scheme had significant positive relationship with the operational safety of the employees $t(95, n= 259)$, 9.987, $p. > .05$. The study concluded that contributory pension scheme and Defined benefit scheme has relationship with the maintenance costs and operational safety of the employees. The study recommended among others. The management of both government and private organizations should participate effectively in contributory pension scheme as this will provide an avenue for all citizens to take control of their financial destinies.*

Keywords: Public/Private Sector, Sustainability, Contributory Pension, Scheme & Maintenance Costs.

INTRODUCTION

1.1 Background of the study

The Administration of Pension in Nigeria have experienced inconsistency in policies due to its many challenges since inception- delay in payment of pensions and gratuities to deserving retirees in

Nigeria fueled by lack of accountability, poor leadership, embezzlement of pension fund, inaccurate pensioners records and gross incompetence on the path of Pension Administrators (Adedoyin, 2023). Reforming the pension system in order to make it more sustainable is a major challenge throughout the country, particularly in a context marked by the retirement of the baby boom generation. Although we have tools as economists to assess whether a particular reform can help improve the systems sustainability, the path ahead is shrouded in uncertainty. The sustainability of the pension system depends largely on the relationship between public pensions and the level of wages in the economy, although it also depends on certain labour policies, such as those aimed at boosting employment and productivity (David & Javier, 2023).

An employee who has worked for an organization for some years is entitled to some benefits which could be in form of gratuity and pension payable to such employee by its employer at the time of retirement. A Pension Fund is any collective arrangement or scheme which has the objective of providing retirement benefits for working persons either in the form of regular income during retirement years or a lump sum at retirement. Pension Funds are usually established by the constitution with the declaration that the funds would be managed in accordance with the rules governing the fund (Abdulkadir, 2015). The reason why Employers offer pension benefit is mainly to attract Employees; meanwhile, Employees rely on retirement benefits as a form of financial security during period of retirement. Pensions could discourage labor turnover. If both the employees and employers contribute to the scheme, then it serves as a general area of joint interest and cooperation and therefore helps to foster better employment relations (Sterns, 2006).

The Contributory Pension Scheme in Nigeria is a groundbreaking initiative that has revolutionized the nation's pension system. This scheme represents a fundamental shift from the previous defined benefit scheme to a more sustainable and efficient defined contribution system (Oak, 2017). Taking an active role in the development of one's team demonstrates confidence and concern for the future of the organization. It also gives employees feelings of significance, community and value – which are always important and even more so in today's work environment when so many companies struggle to attract and keep top talent. It is at this end that the study aimed to evaluate public/private sector involvement and sustainability of contributory pension scheme in Nigeria.

1.2 Statement of the problem

Pensions have effects on the labor market, economic growth, the distribution of risk, and the distribution of income, including by generation and gender. Analysis needs to consider the pension system as a whole, including its multiple objectives and all of the constituent parts of the system. One of the significant advantages of the Contributory Pension Scheme in Nigeria is its stringent regulation and oversight. Despite its success, there are concerns about the adequacy of pension benefits and the need to continually review the contribution rates to ensure that retirees can maintain their desired standard of living.

The major weaknesses of pension scheme was lack of adequate and timely budgetary provision coupled with decreasing life expectancy, increasing number of employers, poor implementation of pension scheme in the private sector due to inadequate supervision and regulation of the system and too many private sector employees were not even covered by the form of pension scheme. While safeguarding the future by boosting the retirement benefits of workers- there is a neglect of what the employee takes home after making the contribution of 8% and paying taxes among other lawful deductions. From the study, it deduced that the challenges of pension scheme occur as a result of poor planning and execution of contributory pension and benefit schemes.

There is no doubt that the best way to ensure retirement security is via the contributory pension scheme (CPS), which offers a superior alternative. In an era marked by economic uncertainties and shifting demographics, the need for a robust and sustainable pension system has never been more critical. These challenges ought to be tackled as it can hinder the maintenance costs and operational safety of individuals who are in the workforce. Hence, the need to evaluate public/private sector involvement and sustainability of contributory pension scheme in Nigeria

1.3 Objective of the study

The main objective of the study was to evaluate public private sector involvement and sustainability of contributory pension scheme in Nigeria. The specific objectives are to:

- i. Examine the relationship between the contributory pension scheme and maintenance costs of employees
- ii. Assess the relationship between the defined benefit scheme and the operational safety of employees

1.4 Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study

- i. What is the relationship between contributory pension scheme and maintenance costs of the employees?
- ii. What is the relationship between defined benefit scheme and operational safety of the employees?

1.5 Statement of the Hypotheses

The following hypothesis guided the study

- i. Contributory pension scheme has no positive relationship with the maintenance costs of the employees
- ii. Defined benefit scheme has no positive relationship with the operational safety of the employees

1.6 Significance of the study

Employees contributing to the pension scheme can benefit by understanding how the involvement of both public and private sectors impacts the long-term value of their retirement savings and ensures their financial security in retirement.

Pensioners who are already receiving pensions can benefit from insights into how the scheme can be made more sustainable, ensuring that they will continue to receive their entitlements in the future.

Scholars and academic institutions studying pension systems, public administration, economics, and finance can use the findings to further academic research, case studies, and policy recommendations that could improve the sustainability of pension schemes in developing economies like Nigeria.

1.7 Scope of the study

The study was based on public/private sector involvement and sustainability of contributory pension scheme in Nigeria. The key variables of the study are contributory pension scheme, benefit scheme, maintenance cost s and operational safety. The area of the study was Nigeria.

REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

2.1 Conceptual Review

2.1.1 Public/private involvement of contributory pension scheme

Contributory Pension Scheme (CPS) is an arrangement where both the employer and the employee contribute a portion of an employee's monthly emolument towards the payment of the employee's pension at retirement. This new scheme covers both public sector and private sector workers, including self-employed individuals. Under the CPS, workers are required to contribute a minimum of 7.5% of their monthly income to their pension fund, while their employers are required to contribute an additional 7.5% (Etim, Umoren & Udo, 2023). The private pension funds in Nigeria are managed by Pension Fund Administrators (PFAs) who are licensed and regulated by PenCom.

2.1.1.1 Contributory pension scheme

Contributory Pension Scheme (CPS) is an arrangement where both the employer and the employee contribute a portion of an employee's monthly emolument towards the payment of the employee's pension at retirement (Pencom, 2020). The Contributory Pension Scheme in Nigeria is a groundbreaking initiative that has revolutionized the nation's pension system. This scheme represents a fundamental shift from the previous defined benefit scheme to a more sustainable and efficient defined contribution system. It aims to secure the financial future of workers, ensuring they can retire with dignity and peace of mind, (Oakpensions, 2023).

2.1.1.2 Defined benefit scheme

A defined-benefit plan is an employer-sponsored retirement plan where employee benefits are computed using a formula that considers several factors, such as length of employment and salary history (Kagan, 2022). A defined benefit (DB) pension scheme is one where the amount you're paid is based on how many years you've been a member of the employer's scheme and the salary you've earned when you leave or retire. Employers contribute to the scheme and are responsible for ensuring

there's enough money at the time of retirement to pay pension income. You can contribute to the scheme too, and, depending on the scheme, this may be a requirement. They usually continue to pay a pension to your spouse, civil partner or dependants when you die, (Moneyhelper, 2023).

2.1.2 Sustainability

Sustainability means meeting our own needs without compromising the ability of future generations to meet their own needs. In addition to natural resources, we also need social and economic resources. Sustainability is not just environmentalism. Embedded in most definitions of sustainability we also find concerns for social equity and economic development. Sustainability refers to the ability to maintain or support a process continuously over time. In business and policy contexts, sustainability seeks to prevent the depletion of natural or physical resources, so that they will remain available for the long term, (Daniel, 2023).

2.1.2.1 Maintenance cost

Maintenance costs refer to the expenses associated with maintaining and preserving the operational functionality of equipment, machinery, and facilities within a manufacturing setting. These costs encompass both direct and indirect expenses incurred in ensuring the reliability, availability, and performance of assets. Understanding these costs is essential for effective financial management and decision-making within the maintenance department.

2.1.2.2 Operational safety

Operational safety is defined as the absence of unacceptable risks, injury or harm to the health of humans, whether direct or indirect, resulting from damage to equipment or the environment. Absence of unreasonable risk under the occurrence of hazards resulting from functional insufficiencies of the intended functionality, operational disturbances or by reasonably foreseeable misuse/errors, (Synergenog, 2024). Operational safety means the absence of unreasonable risk under the occurrence of hazards resulting from functional insufficiencies of the intended, (Lawinsider, 2024).

2.1.3 Conceptual framework of the study

Source: Researcher, 2024

2.2 Theoretical Framework

2.2.1 Expectancy Theory

Expectancy theory was proposed by Victor H. Vroom (1964). Expectancy theory (or expectancy theory of motivation) proposes that an individual will behave or act in a certain way because they are motivated to select a specific behavior over others due to what they expect the result of that selected behavior will be. In essence, the motivation of the behavior selection is determined by the desirability of the outcome.

The study was anchored on this theory because it was emphasizing on the connection between effort, rewards, and goals. People are motivated to work and contribute when they believe they'll achieve a positive outcome and be rewarded for their efforts. Expectancy theory is about the mental processes regarding choice or choosing. It explains the processes that an individual undergoes to make choices. This theory emphasizes the need for organizations to relate rewards directly to performance and to ensure that the rewards provided are deserved and wanted by the recipients (Montana & Charnov, 2008). Expectancy theory operates on the premise that employee's base an individual level of effort on what is necessary to perform well and earn rewards within the workplace. If you want workers to put forth a certain level of effort, set up a reward structure with clear, defined goals and routine evaluations. Employee's need to know as much as possible, the actions necessary to reach a required level of performance, and the amount of effort required should be challenging, but not impossible, if you want morale to stay high while goals are pursued.

2.3 Empirical review

2.3.1 Examination of contributory pension scheme and maintenance cost of the employees

Nwanne (2015) conducted a study on the impact of contributory pension scheme on economic growth in Nigeria for the period 2004-2012. The objectives of the study were to determine the impact of pension funds on economic growth and as well as to ascertain the impact of pension savings mobilized on economic growth. The study used Ex-post-facto research design. Ordinary Least Square Regression method was used in data analysis. The study finds that pension funds have negative and significant impact on economic growth while pension savings had positive and significant impact on economic growth.

Ahmed, Abayomi & Alaka (2016) conducted a study on some of the justification for the contributory pension scheme as part of its values and determined their implications for public servants productivity and pensioners welfare in Lagos State. The methodology employed to achieve these objectives was carried out through primary source of information and personal interview. The primary source involved field survey that consists of administering questionnaire. The sample size is one hundred and twenty respondents (120). The data collected was analyzed statistically in form of tabular presentation with the aid of Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) version 21. Two hypotheses were tested. The result of the analyses reveals that there is significant relationship

between adequate retirement package and employees' productivity and that it has a positive impact on the organization efficiency.

Odo & Okeke (2016) conducted a study on the influence of the contributory pension scheme on the financial system development in Nigeria. Evidence accumulated from both theoretical and empirical literature point to the power of contributory pension to deepen the financial system. An empirical work earlier done showed that the total domestic savings (TDS) increased during the post-pension period; and that the capital market capitalization rose significantly over the period. It was also observed that its implementation has created an impressive scenario whereby now pension funds account for 30% and 8% bond and stock markets capitalization, respectively.

Abiodun, Oyetola, Ibraheem, Omoniyi & Amolegbe, (2020) conducted a study on the role of contributory pension scheme on workers' savings. The objectives of this work includes to determine the impact of contributory pension scheme on workers saving, examine problems hinders effectiveness of contributory Pension scheme and asses effort of government at ensuring efficiency of the contribution pension. The research methods used in the work is survey statistics. The simple random sampling technique was used to select respondents from the ten (10) Local Government Areas (LGAs) in Osun West Senatorial District. The data was analyzed using simple frequency and percentages while the hypotheses formulated were tested and analyzed using the chi-square statistics. The result of hypotheses using chi-square show that contributory pension scheme have impact on workers saving, there is problems hinders effectiveness of Contributory pension scheme, also government is sensitive towards efficiency of contributory pension scheme.

Abdullahi, Obadare, & Anifowose, (2022) conducted a study to provide empirical evidence on the effect of contributory pension scheme on economic growth in Nigeria. Data for the study were secondary sourced from various records of PenCom Annual Reports and CBN Bulletin (database). The data were computed with the use of Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS). It was concluded that pension fund assets and pension contribution /savings mobilized over the years have positive and insignificant impact on economic growth.

2.3.2 Assessment of defined benefit scheme and operational safety of the employees

Okechukwu, Nebo, Eze (2016) conducted a study on Management of pension schemes in Nigeria has been characterized by multiple and diverse problems despite several modifications of the pension schemes by the government. The study examined the extent strategies adopted for pension management can enhance employees' confidence in the scheme. The study adopted a survey design. The data were analyzed using tables, frequencies, and mean. Z- Test was used to test the hypotheses at 0.05 significance. It was revealed that to a very large extent strategies adopted for pension and retirement management can enhance employees' confidence in the management of the schemes.

Ibeme, & Aniche (2016) conducted a study on the implementation of the 2004 pension ACT in Enugu State Civil Service with a view to proffering solutions. Pension administration and prompt payment of pensioners have become a serious problem in Nigeria. In the course of conducting this research, descriptive survey research was used. Data were collected using questionnaire, face to face interview and focus group discussion. Hypotheses formulated were tested using Chi-square non parametric statistics. The study revealed among other things that the government of Enugu State has not put efficient financial control mechanism in place to ensure efficiency in pension fund management.

Okwor, Ndu, Arinze-Onyia, Ogugua, Obionu, Agwu-Umahi, Okeke & Aguwa (2020) conducted a study on work environment is rapidly changing and in recent times, occupational stress poses a threat to the health, morale and productivity of workers and the organization. This study sought to determine the prevalence and predictors of stress among bankers in a south-eastern state of Nigeria. A descriptive cross-sectional study was carried out among 370 bankers in Enugu State, Nigeria using the Health, Safety, Executive (HSE) management standards indicator tool. Multistage sampling method was used to select participants. Statistical analysis was done using SPSS 22.0. Level of statistical significance was set at $p < 0.05$. The mean age of the participants was 34.54 ± 6.3 years while the mean years of work was 6.01 ± 4.7 years. One hundred and seventy-four (47%) reported high level of stress due to relationship at work while 318 (85.9%) reported low level of stress due to roles. Being 35 years or less was found to a predictor of high (AOR 0.55, CI 0.30-1.02) level of stress due to control. Work experience of 5 years or less was found to be a predictor of both high (AOR 0.74, CI 0.40--1.37) and low (AOR 0.99, CI 0.40-1.37) levels of stress due to control.

Obikeze & Onwujekwe, (2020) conducted a study on health maintenance organizations (HMOs) are the purchasers of health insurance with a social National Health Insurance Scheme for civil servants. However the roles of HMOs in implementation of social health insurance are not clear. This study determined the roles of HMOs in implementation of the national social health insurance scheme in Enugu, Southeast Nigeria. A partially mixed sequential dominant status design was employed in the study. Quantitative data were collected from 613 Federal Government employees that are registered with the National Health Insurance Scheme (NHIS) as part of the Formal Sector Social Health Insurance Program (FSSHIP) using an interviewer-administered questionnaire. Test for sampling adequacy was ensured (KMO, 0.701) and likewise the sphericity of the data using Bartlett's test (Chi [1] 796.72, p -value < 0.001). For the qualitative study, there was document review and in-depth interviews. A total of 28 in-depth interviews were conducted with key stakeholders comprising of managers of HMOs, NHIS manager, providers of health care and personnel in the State Ministry of Health among others. Thematic analysis was used for the qualitative data. One-third (31.5%) of respondents said that roles of HMOs were very important, while 23% said that their roles were not important. More than half (57.70%) ranked HMOs very low in their roles, while 24.10% ranked them highest. Concentration index shows that the poor were satisfied (-.10), while the rich were highly satisfied (0.13) with roles of HMOs.

Obinwune, Ohanyere & Anah, (2023) conducted a study on occupational health and safety management practices and employee' productivity of lubricant firms in Anambra State, Nigeria. The objectives were to examine the effect of occupational health and safety management practices on employee' productivity of lubricant firms in Anambra State. The study adopted survey research; data were generated from primary and secondary sources. The method for data collection was questionnaire which was administered randomly among the staff of the selected firms. The population of the study was 1220, the sample size of the study was two hundred and thirty-four (234). While one hundred and eighty-three (183) were retrieved. The hypotheses were tested using multiple regression analysis method at 0.05% level of significance. The findings of the study revealed that, Health and Safety training has significant positive effect on employee' productivity of lubricant firms in Anambra State ($t=2.136$, p , 011). Risk management has significant positive effect on employee' productivity of

lubricant firms in Anambra State, ($t=3.292$, $p, 009$) Management commitment to safety has significant positive effect on employee' productivity of lubricant firms in Anambra State, ($t=4.505$, $p, 000$).

2.4 Summary and Gap in Empirical Review

The studies done were carried outside public/private sector involvement and sustainability of contributory pension scheme in Nigeria and did not focus to best of my knowledge on the contributory pension scheme and maintenance costs; and defined benefit scheme and operational safety of the employees. Most of the studies reviewed analyzed their data through A purposeful sampling technique, Descriptive statistics and appropriate inferential statistics, Purposive Sampling technique, Pearson Moment Correlation Coefficient, Multiple sampling technique, Multiple Regression Analysis (MRA) method, Simple linear regression and Pearson correlation coefficient (r) while the present study made use of t - test to test the hypotheses. Therefore, the study aimed at filling this research gap by evaluating the Public/private sector involvement and sustainability of contributory pension scheme in Nigeria.

METHODOLOGY

3.1 Research Design

The study employed descriptive survey design. The survey design was adopted because the study requires a technique of observation such as questionnaire and or interview, the population of the study must be carefully chosen, clearly defined and specifically delimited and roles upon observation for the acquisition of data.

3.2 Source of Data

Data are classified as either primary or secondary data. The classification was based on the two possible sources: primary source and secondary source.

3.2.1 Primary Source

The primary source were the employees who has worked for an organization for some years and is entitled to some benefits which could be in form of gratuity and pension payable to such employee by its employer or an agent at the time of retirement or withdrawal of service. The administration of questionnaire was used.

3.2.2 Sources of Secondary Data

Secondary data source is the one which the data is obtained from published materials, internet websites, reports, dailies, text books and so on from the library of the institutions understudy. Sources of secondary can be split into two parts internal and external sources.

3.3 Area of Study

The area of the study was Enugu Metropolis, Enugu State, Nigeria.

3.4 Population of the Study

The study population was two hundred and seventy one (271) comprising of retirees and potential retirees from Enugu metropolis.

3.5 Sample Size Determination

The whole population was used due to small number

3.6. Sampling Technique

The simple random sampling with a random start was adopted so as to give everybody equal opportunity of being selected into sample.

3.7 Instrument for Data Collection

The main instrument for data collection was a structured questionnaire. Copies of the questionnaire were administered to the respondents. Ten (10) designed questionnaire was used. The responses generated were used thereafter for data analyses.

3.8 Validity of the Instrument

The instrument was given to two experts from the industry and academia to measure face and content validity. To make sure that the research instruments applied in the work are valid, the research ensured that the instrument measure the concept they are supposed to measure.

3.9 Reliability of the Research Instrument

This was done by administering 20 copies of the prepared questionnaire to the sample of the study. Cronbah's Alpha was used in determining the extent of consistency of the reliability. A Cronbach's alpha value (∞) of greater 0.810 indicated very strong reliability.

Scale: ALL VARIABLES

Case Processing Summary

		N	%
Cases	Valid	10	100.0
	Excluded	0	.0
	Total	10	100.0

a. Listwise deletion based on all variables in the procedure.

Reliability Statistics

Cronbach's Alpha	No. of Items
.810	10

Scale reliabilities were calculated using Cronbach's Alpha; the result obtained was 0.810. This shows that the internal consistency of the scale is good for the purpose of this study because it is greater than 0.740 which was good.

3.10 Method of Data Analyses

Data from the questionnaire were analyzed with the aid of SPSS version 23 using simple, percentages and correlation co-efficient. Data from the questionnaire were further analyzed using simple percentages, mean and standard deviation. For the 5-point likert scale questions, the scale and decision rule stated below were used in analyzing the findings.

Scale: Strongly Agree (SA) = 5, Agree (A) = 4, Neutral (N) = 3, Disagree (D) = 2, Strongly Disagree (SD) = 1.

Decision Rule: If Mean ≥ 3.0 , the respondents agree and If mean ≤ 3.0 , the respondents disagree. The decision rule is to accept the null hypothesis if the computed r is less than the tabulated r otherwise rejects the null hypothesis and Z - test was used to test the hypotheses and analyzed with the aid of SPSS.

DATA PRESENTATION, ANALYSES AND INTERPRETATION

4.1 Distribution and Returned Questionnaire

The chapter presents and analyzes the data collected for the study. The presentation and interpretation of data were based on the questionnaire administrated to the retirees and potential retirees under study.

Table 4.1 Distribution and Return of the Questionnaire

Firms	Distributed	No Returned	percent	No not Returned	Percent
1. The retirees and potential retirees	271	259	96	12	4
Total	271	259	96	12	4

Source: Field Survey, 2024

Two hundred and seventy one (271) copies of the questionnaire were distributed to the respondents and two hundred and fifty nine (259) copies were returned representing Ninety six(96) percent, while twelve (12) copies of the questionnaire were not returned representing four (4) percent. That showed a high rate of response.

4.2 Data Presentation

4.2.1 The relationship between contributory pension scheme and maintenance costs of the employees

Table 4.2.1: Responses on the relationship between contributory pension scheme and maintenance costs of the employees

	5 SA	4 A	3 N	2 DA	1 SD	ΣFX	- X	SD	Decision
1 Contributory pension scheme provides a guaranteed annual income for life.	475 95 36.7	80 20 7.7	249 83 32.0	78 39 15.1	22 22 8.5	904 259 100%	3.49	1.342	Agree
2 Based on final or average salary it gives opportunities for investment	715 143 55.2	80 20 7.7	117 39 15.1	62 31 12.0	26 26 10.0	1000 259 100%	3.86	1.440	Agree
3 The investment of pension fund creates job opportunities.	565 113 43.6	84 21 8.1	213 71 27.4	52 26 10.0	28 28 10.8	942 259 100%	3.64	1.400	Agree
4 Stimulation of entrepreneurship is promoted by contributory fund	610 122 47.1	218 54 20.8	99 33 12.7	52 26 10.0	24 24 9.3	1003 259 100%	3.86	1.350	Agree
5 The contributory pension scheme offers greater transparency and flexibility, allowing workers to monitor it	765 153 59.1	148 37 14.3	66 22 8.5	52 26 10.0	21 21 8.1	1052 259 100%	4.06	1.345	Agree
Total Grand mean and standard deviation							3.782	1.3754	

Source: Field Survey, 2024

Table 4.2.1, 115 respondents out of 259 representing 44.4 percent agreed that Contributory pension scheme provides a guaranteed annual income for life with mean score 3.49 and standard deviation of 1.342. Based on final or average salary it gives opportunities for investment 163 respondents representing 62.9 percent agreed with mean score of 3.86 and standard deviation of 1.440. The investment of pension fund creates job opportunities 134 respondents representing 51.7 percent agreed with mean score of 3.64 and standard deviation of 1.400. Stimulation of entrepreneurship is promoted by contributory fund 176 respondents representing 67.9 percent agreed with mean score of 3.86 and 1.350. The contributory pension scheme offers greater transparency and flexibility, allowing workers to monitor it 190 respondents representing 73.4 percent agreed with a mean score of 4.06 and standard deviation 1.345

4.2.2 The relationship between defined benefit scheme and operational safety of the employees

Table 4.2.2.1: Responses on the relationship between defined benefit scheme and operational safety of the employees

		5 SA	4 A	3 N	2 DA	1 SD	∑FX	- X	SD	Decision
1	A guaranteed income based on set calculations enhances improved staff relations.	510 102 39.4	260 65 25.1	54 18 6.9	96 48 18.2	26 26 10.0	946 259 100%	3.65	1.412	Agree
2	There is a fixed payout on defined benefit scheme which improve employee morale	585 117 45.2	360 90 34.7	279 19 7.3	26 13 5.0	20 20 7.7	1270 259 100%	4.05	1.193	Agree
3	Protection from market fluctuations facilitates cost saving.	730 146 56.4	284 71 27.4	54 18 6.9	12 6 2.3	18 18 6.9	1098 259 100%	4.24	1.140	Agree
4	The increase in employed retention through defined benefit scheme promotes reputation	635 127 49.0	348 87 33.6	39 13 5.0	54 18 6.9	14 14 5.4	1090 259 100%	4.14	1.136	Agree
5	Defined benefit plan offers employees the security and improves business efficiency.	420 84 32.4	428 107 41.3	39 13 5.0	76 38 14.7	17 17 6.6	980 259 100%	3.78	1.229	Agree
Total Grand mean and standard deviation								3.638	1.497	

Source: Field Survey, 2024

Table 4.2.2.1, 167 respondents out of 259 representing 64.5 percent agreed that A guaranteed income based on set calculations enhances improved staff relations with mean score 3.65 and standard deviation of 1.412. There is a fixed payout on defined benefit scheme which improve employee morale 207 respondents representing 79.9 percent agreed with mean score of 4.05 and standard deviation of

1.193. Protection from market fluctuations facilitates cost saving 217 respondents representing 83.8 percent agreed with mean score of 4.24 and standard deviation of 1.140. The increase in employed retention through defined benefit scheme promotes reputation 214 respondents representing 82.6 percent agreed with mean score of 4.14 and 1.136. Defined benefit plan offers employees the security and improves business efficiency 191 respondents representing 73.7 percent agreed with a mean score of 3.78 and standard deviation 1.229.

4.3 Test of hypotheses

4.3.1 Contributory pension scheme has no positive relationship with the maintenance costs of the employees

Table 4.3.1: Shows t - test on Contributory pension scheme has no positive relationship with the maintenance costs of the employees

Contingency Table 4.3.1.1 of Research Question one:

S/N		SA	A	N	D	SD
1.	Contributory pension scheme provides a guaranteed annual income for life.	95	20	83	39	22
2.	Based on final or average salary it gives opportunities for investment	143	20	39	31	26
3.	The investment of pension fund creates job opportunities.	113	21	71	26	28
4.	Stimulation of entrepreneurship is promoted by contributory fund	122	54	33	26	24
5	The contributory pension scheme offers greater transparency and flexibility, allowing workers to monitor it	153	37	22	26	21
	Total	626	152	248	148	121

Table 4.3.1.2 Contingency table of cumulative responses of Research Question One

Options	χ	F	F χ	$\bar{\chi} - \chi = \chi_1$	F(χ_1) ²	$\Sigma f(\chi_1)^2$
Strongly agree	5	626	3,130	-1.216	626 x (-1.216) ²	925.639
Agree	4	157	628	-.217	157 x (-.217) ²	7.393
Neutral	3	248	744	.783	248 x (.783) ²	152.046
Disagree	2	148	296	1.783	148 x (1.783) ²	470.505
Strongly Disagree	1	121	121	2.783	121 x (2.783) ²	937.156
	15	1300	4,919			2492.739

Mean score

$$\bar{\chi} = \frac{F\chi}{N} = \frac{4919}{1300} = 3.783$$

$$\text{Variance} = (S^2) = \frac{\Sigma f(\chi_1)^2}{N-1} = \frac{2492.739}{1299} = 1.919$$

$$\text{Standard deviation} = \sqrt{S^2} = \sqrt{1.919} = 1.385$$

$$\text{Level of confidence} = 0.05$$

$$\mu = \text{Population mean} = 3.0$$

$$\text{Statistical tool used} = t - \text{test}$$

$$t = \frac{\bar{x} - \mu}{\frac{s}{\sqrt{n}}}$$

Where;

μ = Population mean

s = Sample standard deviation

n = Sample size 259

Level of significance: α at 5%

Degree of freedom: $\frac{K-1}{N-K} = \frac{5-1}{259-5} = (254, 4) = 1.96$

t - tabulated value = 1.96

Decision Rule:

If the t-calculated is greater than the t-tabulated {t-cal > t-tab} reject the null hypothesis {H₀} that the overall estimate is not significant and if otherwise conclude that the overall estimate is statistically significant.

Substituting $t = \frac{\bar{x} - \mu}{\frac{s}{\sqrt{n}}}$ $t = \frac{3.783 - 3.0}{\frac{1.385}{\sqrt{259}}} = \frac{.783}{\frac{1.385}{16.093}} = \frac{.783 \times 16.093}{1.385}$, t = 9.098

The computed t = 9.098 greater than the table value of 1.96, we reject the null hypothesis. Therefore, we concluded that contributory pension scheme had significant positive relationship with the maintenance costs of the employees reported in the probability value of (t = 9.098, p. > .05).

4.3.2 Defined benefit scheme has relationship with the operational safety of the employees

Table 4.3.2: Shows t – test on Defined benefit scheme has relationship with the operational safety of the employees

Contingency Table 4.3.2.1 of Research Question two:

S/N		SA	A	N	D	SD
1.	A guaranteed income based on set calculations enhances improved staff relations.	102	65	18	48	26
2.	There is a fixed payout on defined benefit scheme which improve employee morale	117	90	19	13	20
3.	Protection from market fluctuations facilitates cost saving.	146	71	18	6	18
4.	The increase in employed retention through defined benefit scheme promotes reputation	127	87	13	18	14
5	Defined benefit plan offers employees the security and improves business efficiency.	84	107	13	38	17
	Total	576	420	81	123	95

Table 4.3.2.2 Contingency table of cumulative responses of Research Question two

Options	χ	F	F χ	$\bar{\chi} - \chi = \chi_1$	F(χ_1) ²	$\Sigma f(\chi_1)^2$
Strongly agree	5	576	2880	-1.043	576 x (-1.043) ²	626.601
Agree	4	420	1680	-.043	420 x (-.043) ²	.777
Neutral	3	81	243	.957	81 x (.957) ²	74.184
Disagree	2	123	246	1.957	123 x (1.957) ²	471.071
Strongly Disagree	1	95	95	2.957	95 x (2.957) ²	830.666
	15	1300	5,144			2,003.299

Mean score

$$\bar{X} = \frac{FX}{N} = \frac{5144}{1300} = 3.957$$

$$\text{Variance} = (S^2) = \frac{\sum f(\chi_1)^2}{N-1} = \frac{2003.299}{1299} = 1.542$$

$$\text{Standard deviation} = \sqrt{S^2} = \sqrt{1.542} = 1.242$$

$$\text{Level of confidence} = 0.05$$

$$\mu = \text{Population mean} = 3.0$$

$$\text{Statistical tool used} = t - \text{test}$$

$$t = \frac{\bar{X} - \mu}{\frac{s}{\sqrt{n}}}$$

Where;

$$\mu = \text{Population mean}$$

$$s = \text{Sample standard deviation}$$

$$n = \text{Sample size } 259$$

Level of significance: α at 5%

$$\text{Degree of freedom: } \frac{N-1}{K-N} = \frac{5-1}{259-5} = (209, 4) = 1.96$$

$$t - \text{tabulated value} = 1.96$$

Decision Rule:

If the t-calculated is greater than the t-tabulated {t-cal > t-tab} reject the null hypothesis {H₀} that the overall estimate is not significant and if otherwise conclude that the overall estimate is statistically significant.

$$\text{Substituting } t = \frac{\bar{X} - \mu}{\frac{s}{\sqrt{n}}}$$

$$t = \frac{3.957 - 3.0}{\frac{1.542}{\sqrt{259}}} = \frac{.957}{\frac{1.542}{16.093}} = \frac{.957 \times 16.093}{1.542} \quad t = 9.987$$

The computed $t = 9.987$ greater than the table value of 1.96, we reject the null hypothesis. Therefore, we concluded that Defined benefit scheme had significant positive relationship with the operational safety of the employees, as reported in the probability value of ($t = 9.987, p. > .05$).

4.4 Discussion of Findings

4.4.1 Contributory pension scheme has relationship with the maintenance costs of the employees

From the result of hypothesis one, the computed $t = 9.098$ greater than the table value of 1.96, the study concluded that Contributory pension scheme had significant positive relationship with the maintenance costs of the employees reported in the probability value of ($t = 9.098, p. > .05$). In the support of the result in the literature view, Nwanne (2015) conducted a study on the impact of

contributory pension scheme on economic growth in Nigeria for the period 2004-2012. The study finds that pension funds have negative and significant impact on economic growth while pension savings had positive and significant impact on economic growth. There is also a significant relationship between adequate retirement package and employees' productivity and that it has a positive impact on the organization efficiency (Ahmed, Abayomi & Alaka, 2016)

4.4.2 Defined benefit scheme has relationship with the operational safety of the employees

From the result of hypothesis two, the computed $t = 9.987$ greater than the table value of 1, 96, the study concluded that Defined benefit scheme had significant positive relationship with the operational safety of the employees, as reported in the probability value of ($t = 9.987, p. > .05$). In the support of the result in the literature view, among other things that the government of Enugu State has not put efficient financial control mechanism in place to ensure efficiency in pension fund management. Okechukwu, Nebo, Eze (2016) conducted a study on management of pension schemes in Nigeria has been characterized by multiple and diverse problems despite several modifications of the pension schemes by the government. It was revealed that to a very large extent strategies adopted for pension and retirement management can enhance employees' confidence in the management of the schemes.

SUMMARY OF THE FINDINGS, CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

5.1 Summary of the Findings

Based on the results the following findings were made:

- i. Contributory pension scheme had positive relationship with the maintenance costs of the employees $t(95, n= 259), 9.098, p. > .05$
- ii. Defined benefit scheme had positive relationship with the operational safety of the employees $t(95, n= 259), 9.987, p. > .05$.

5.2 Conclusion

The study concluded that Contributory pension scheme and Defined benefit scheme had positive relationship with the maintenance costs and operational safety of the employees. The pension scheme promote saving culture among Nigerian workers and wider coverage of Nigerian workers. Pension fund contribution is effective in stimulating growth through investment in portfolios that yield short term returns; this implies that pension fund contribution cannot on its own without a credible financial system impact on economic growth.

5.3 Recommendations

Based on the findings, the following recommendations were proffered

- i. The management of both government and private organizations should participate effectively in Contributory pension scheme as this will provide an avenue for all citizens to take control of their financial destinies.
- ii. There is need for all employees to endeavour to be involved in the Defined Benefits Scheme, as this will encourage and provide retirees with a predictable pension amount based on their salary and years of service. This helps retirees plan their finances better.

5.4 Contribution to Knowledge

The studies done were carried outside public/private sector involvement and sustainability of contributory pension scheme in Nigeria. Most of the studies reviewed analysed their data through Descriptive and inferential statistics, Pearson Moment Correlation Coefficient, Multiple Regression Analysis (MRA) e.t.c. while the present study made use of t - test to test the hypotheses. Therefore, the study aimed at filling this research gap by evaluating the Public/private sector involvement and sustainability of contributory pension scheme in Nigeria.

REFERENCES

- Abdulkadir, M. U. (2015). Impact of contributory pension scheme on worker's investments and savings in Nigeria. *Bingham International Journal of Accounting and Finance (BIJAF)* 404 - 416
- Abdullahi, U. A., Obadare, G. O. & Anifowose, O. L. (2022). Contributory Pension Scheme on Nigerian Economic Growth. *KIU Interdisciplinary Journal of Humanities and Social Sciences*, 3(1), 264-283
- Abiodun, O. W., Oyetola, D. O, Ibraheem, A. A, Omoniyi O. O. & Amolegbe, S. A. (2020). Role of Contributory Pension Scheme on Workers' Savings *International Journal of Academic Management Science Research (IJAMSR)* ISSN: 2643-900X. 4(8), 186-196.
- Adedoyin, A. (2023). Pension Reforms in Nigeria; Benefits & Challenges. <https://www.linkedin.com/pulse/pension-reforms-nigeria-benefits-challenges-adedoyin-adebayo>
- Ahmed, I. K., Abayomi O. A. & Alaka N. S. (2016). Effects of contributory pension scheme on employees' productivity: Evidence from Lagos state government. *African Journal of business management*. 10(16), 384-396. <https://doi.org/10.5897/AJBM2016.8102>
- Daniel, T. M. (2023). What is Sustainability? <https://www.investopedia.com/terms/s/sustainability>.
- David, D. V. and Javier, G. A., (2023) How have other pension systems ensured their sustainability? <https://www.caixabankresearch.com/en/how-have-other-pension-systems-ensured-their-sustainability>
- Etim, R. S., Umoren, A. O. & Udo, N. A. (2023). Influence of Contributory Pension Scheme on Economic Development in Nigeria. *AKSU Journal of Administration and Corporate Governance (AKSUJACOG)*. 3(1), 94-108

Ibeme, P. N. & Aniche, A. (2016). Diagnosing the elephantine problems in the implementation of the 2004 Pension Act in Enugu State Civil Service. *Journal of Policy and Development Studies (JPDS)*. 10(4).

Kagan, J. (2022). What is defined benefit scheme <https://www.investopedia.com/terms/d/defined-benefit-pension-plan.asp>

Lawinsider (2024). Operational safety definition <https://www.lawinsider.com/dictionary/operational-safety>

Moneyhelper (2023). What is defined benefit <https://www.moneyhelper.org.uk/en/pensions-and-retirement/pensions-basics/defined-benefit-or-final-salary-pensions-schemes-explained>

Nwanne, T. F. I. (2015). Impact of Contributory Pension Scheme on Economic Growth in Nigeria *Global Advanced Research Journal of Management and Business Studies* (ISSN: 2315-5086). 4(8), 333-337.

Oakpensions (2023). the contributory pension scheme in Nigeria <https://www.oakpensions.com/empowering-the-future-with-the-contributory-pension-scheme-in-nigeria.aspx>

Oak, P. (2017). The contributory Pension Scheme in Nigeria. <https://www.oakpensions.com/empowering-the-future-with-the-contributory-pension-scheme-in-nigeria.aspx>

Obikeze, E. & Onwujekwe, O. (2020). The roles of health maintenance organizations in the implementation of a social health insurance scheme in Enugu, Southeast Nigeria: a mixed-method investigation. *International Journal for Equity in Health*. Volume 19, Article number: 33 (2020).

Obinwune, C. A., Ohanyere, C. P. & Anah, S. A. (2023). Occupational Health and Safety Management Practice and Employee' Productivity of Lubricant Firms in Anambra State, Nigeria *International Journal of Business Systems and Economics* ISSN: 2360-9923, 13(3), 165 – 180. DOI: 272614527311471 www.arcnjournals.org.

Odo, C. O. & Okeke, C. (2016). The contributory pension scheme and the financial system development in Nigeria *Innovative Marketing*, 12(2), 16-21. doi:10.21511/im.12 (2).2016.02

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Okwor, T. J., Ndu, A.C., Arinze-Onyia, S. U., Ogugua, I. J., Obionu, I. M., Agwu-Umahi, O. R., Okeke, T. A. & Aguwa, E. N. (2020). Prevalence and Predictors of Stress among Bankers in Enugu State South-East Nigeria *Journal of Community Medicine and Primary Health Care*. 32(2), 68-79 <https://dx.doi.org/10.4314/jcmphc.v32i2.6>

Pencom (2020). What is contributory pension scheme? <https://www.pencom.gov.ng/wp-content/uploads/2020/06/FREQUENTLY-ASK-QUESTION-2020-ENGLISH-MAIN VISUAL.pdf>

Sterns, W. L. (2006). Work and Retirement in Older Society in Our Aging Society, Paradox and Promise, A. Pifer and L. Bronte eds, New York: Carnage Corporation. pp. 341-365.

Synergenog (2024). what is operational safety https://synergenog.com/helpie_faq/define-operational-safety/

Wikipedia (2023). What is sustainability? <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Sustainability>